

Re-Examining the Foundational Role of Preamble in Indian Constitution

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Abstract

The place of Preamble in the Constitution of a country is highly important so far as the ideals, aspirations and aims of its people are concerned. Preamble being a preliminary statement implies so many connotations depicting not only socio-cultural and political characteristics of a State, but it also connotes the basic ideals which a state aspires to attain, as well as it contains the enacting statement or clause that whence the Constitution comes into force. Indian Constitution too has a very potential Preamble pregnant with multifarious meanings, connotations and implications, which no other country has. As a preliminary statement to a statute or to the Constitution, Preamble holds the fundamental value. Preamble of the Indian Constitution contains certain foundational features that characterize what an independent democratic country is all about; namely, the political nature of the State and the form of government it is going to have. Preamble quite clearly announces the source of authority that renders this constitution, or in other words where the sovereignty resides which is very manifest with these opening words, "We, the people of India....." Therefore, for running the country certain other ideals, aims are required to be enshrined. These aims or ideals are in trinity i.e. Justice, Equality, Liberty and Fraternity make it more lucrative for a young democratic and multi-lingual and multi-religious country. Therefore, a simple reading of the Preamble of the Constitution of India make it clear enough that the apex judiciary is bound by the underlying philosophy enshrined in the Preamble of our Constitution. Today we are living in an open market economy where even governments are interested in disinvestments, selling its shares to private companies, and let's hope and see that our poor people should not suffer due to this globalization of economic order and preambular words always serve as a reminder for the present Governments to make a balanced approach by which all segments of multi cultural India reap the democratic dividends in equal measure.

Keywords: Preamble, Justice, Equality, Liberty and Fraternity.

Introduction: Preamble as a Preface to the Constitution

The preliminary words with which the Constitution of a country begin is its 'Preamble', which speaks about the basic characteristics of the nature of the State in the political sense, whether it is a democratic republic or otherwise. Secondly, there are certain ideals, aims and objectives of the people of a country for which it struggle hard in its historical past, and now it wants to achieve them through authoritative statements inscribed in Preambular words of the Constitution. Here, in the Indian context of Preambular words and expressions, there are so many implications and connotations attached to its Preamble.

To read the Preamble again, it says :

"We, the people of India, having solemnly resolved to Constitute India into a Sovereign, Socialist, Secular, Democratic Republic and to secure to all citizens :

Justice, social, economic and political

Liberty of thought, expression, belief, faith and worship,

Equality of status and of opportunity; and to promote among them all

Fraternity assuring the **dignity of the individual** and the **unity and integrity** of the nation.

In Our Constituent Assembly this twenty-sixth day of November, 1949, do hereby adopt, enact and give to ourselves this Constitution."

Linguistic Charm of Preambular Declaration

In the sublime view of the author, the very linguistic setting of the whole content of the Preamble of Indian Constitution is very unique as it very succinctly pronounces not only the lego-political character of a newly formed democratic country but it also gives priority to those ideals and perennial goals of million masses who suffered immeasurably at the cruel hands of foreign power, and now, at the very inception of a collective democratic polity these poor people who want to assure themselves with these humanistic and wholesome ideals like **Justice, Liberty, Equality and Fraternity** assuring the dignity of the individual and also the **unity** and the **integrity** of the nation. It all demonstrates the broad-based vision of our Constitution-makers who not only sought to make Indian State into a well-intentioned welfarist, socialist and secular country, but also to make the lives of Indian people happy, secure and free from the hundreds of years of slavery and this has been done by enshrining highly placed ideals of an ideal independent society, i.e. by granting constitutional guarantee of freedom, justice, equality and fraternity to all citizens of India irrespective of their religion, caste, colour, sex, place of birth or on any other ground.

One thing very first in the preferential order of our Preamble is the beginning with the words 'We the people of India.....' which means that from now on the cherished sovereign power will be exercised by the Indian people themselves, which they can enjoy through their democratic representatives, and be governed by their own choice. Through this linguist expression, preamble itself speaks very manifestly about the prospective governance pattern of a young nation who shall democratically run its affairs on its own will and genius.

What Preamble Does

Here we talk of the Preamble of the Indian Constitution. Preamble itself doesn't confer any power in the Constitution, but it only directs the aims and objectives sought to be archived as under –

- a) Preamble pronounces the kind of Government and Polity of the Country;
- b) It announces the different Rights and Freedoms to be enjoyed by the people of India;
- c) And it (the Preamble) contains the enacting clause which brings about the enforcement of the Constitution.

The Effect of the Constitution (42nd Amendment) Act, 1976

This Amendment to the Indian Constitution brought about the two words "Socialist and Secular". The word 'Socialist' is very much preferred expression of all socialistic countries, which means and includes the basic obligation on the part of such country to bestow upon the best on the toiling and poor masses, so that they no longer become victim of injustice and oppressions of any kind at the hand of feudal lords and cruel capitalists. But the word 'Socialism' was never given a uniform meaning and definition for all to follow. In actual parlance, the general ownership of the means of production and distribution will be in the control of the State and not in the hands of capitalist bosses. Yet another word 'Secularism' means a State that adopts no religion of its own; meaning thereby, the state is obligated to give equally the same treatment to all religions within its territory.

There is yet another set of twin words and expressions 'Democratic' and 'Republic', which respectively means that type of Government which derives its authority from the 'real will' of the people. And the word 'Republic' denotes that there shall be an 'Elected Head' of the State who will be the Chief Executive Head. As in India, the President is the Chief Executive Head.

Significance of the Expressions – Justice, Liberty, Equality and Fraternity

Now we will briefly explain the above stated expressions separately – Justice – This word has been qualified by the terms social, economic and political. It means our constitutional fathers thought of 'justice' in a very wide and pragmatic manner comprising the spirit of dispensing justice not only at the individual level but also attempting to eliminate injustice which is socially done (in the form social disparities); also injustice done economically (poor remaining poor at the hands of capitalist model) and also eliminating political injustice (by and giving proper representation to poor people or people who are socially and educationally backward. So we see all honesty on the part of our constitution-authors who really wanted to remove inequalities of all sorts and they wanted to establish 'Egalitarian' order in Indian soil. 'Justice', broadly speaking, is not merely justice being done to an individual, but it (justice) is looking to the general welfare of society, therefore, it becomes a happy combination of taking an overall balanced approach towards each one's interests alongside the interests of others.

Moreover the expression 'Social Justice' is the removal of all kinds of inequalities irrespective of the considerations of race, religion, caste and so on and so forth. The expression '**economic justice**' means equal payment for equal work done as all are entitled for their just and fair labour irrespective of any other considerations. In the like manner, 'political justice' means giving political power to all sections of society without any distinction on the ground of caste, race, sex, religion, place of birth.

As regards '**Liberty**', it means giving certain fundamental freedom to individual for full realization of his personality on the one hand; and on the other hand, it means absence of any kind of undue interference in an individual's life on part of the State. This way liberty is sought to be fully protected through State in its widest possible extent.

As regards '**Equality**', Indian Constitution not merely secures it irrespective of status, but also accords 'equal opportunity' to everybody irrespective of any religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth, and this has been made possible through giving access to all public places to all citizens. Equality has been ensured through so equal opportunity in respect of Employment to any office of the State.

As regards '**Fraternity**', it means the connotation of common brotherhood of all belonging to Indian soil. There are certain provisions in our constitution that produces the high spirit of brotherhood among Indian folk i.e., **the provision of common citizenship, right to move freely in any part of the country; to reside and settle in any part of Indian territory; and also to practise any profession or to carry on any occupation, trade or business in India.**

Interpretative Aid of 'Preamble' in our Constitution

In *Berubari Union Case*⁽¹⁾ Supreme Court treated the 'Preamble' not as part of the Constitution on the premise that the preamble has not been enacted in the same manner in which the other provisions of the constitution are enacted and adopted. But one celebrated author⁽²⁾ says that it (preamble) was enacted and adopted in the same manner as the rest of the Constitution, it is another fact that the preamble was passed only after draft articles of the Constitution were adopted along with such modification as were approved by the Constituent Assembly.

In *Keshvanand Bharti Vs. State of Kerala*⁽³⁾, the Court took the contrary view to the previous position as stated in *Berubari case*, and said that "the preamble of the Constitution was part of the Constitution and the observations to the contrary in *Berubari Union case* were not correct."

One thing very important in this regard is that when the enacting words of the Constitution are clear enough or unambiguous, the Preamble cannot be resorted to control, qualify or restrict any meaning of the Constitution. In one important case⁽⁴⁾ it is made clear that "It (Preamble) can be used where the enactment is not clear."

A five Bench Constitutional Bench in one important case⁽⁵⁾ proceeded even more steps towards strengthening the position of Preamble when it dealt with the principles of secularism, democracy and social justice in an overriding effect in the sense that all these principles put together lend linking factor for the fundamental rights in part III of the Constitution, (Articles, 14, 19 & 21) and hence equating the Preamble with other provisions of the Constitution with ensuring its place as an essential feature of the Constitution of India. Having passed many labyrinthine routes, it is quite explicitly clear that Preamble is very much part and pared of the Constitution.

Impact of Changed Economic Order on the Interpretation of the Constitution

Ever since the inception of our constitution 'Socialistic Pattern' was adopted in relation to Indian Economy where ownership or control of means of production and its distribution was principally in the hands of public sector which was aimed at eliminating inequalities of status, and to ensure a decent standard of life to the working people. But after the opening of market economy, the global world order had changed, and Judiciary also began to be influenced by privatization of public sector. In one very important case, the words of Supreme Court are noteworthy in terms of disinvestment of Government Company, and the Court observed⁽⁶⁾ :

"With the change in economic climate, the wisdom and manner for Government to run commercial ventures may require reconsideration. What may have been in public interest at a point of time may no longer be so."

With the advancement of time, the judicial trend is also tilting towards change in economic thinking which is sidelining socialism in the country. In one more case this trend becomes quite apparent, and it is visible from the following words of Supreme Court when it says : "Socialism may be present in the Preamble in our Constitution. However, due to liberalization policy adopted by the Central Government from the early nineties, this view that Indian society is essentially wedded to socialism is definitely withering away."

However, it can be fairly said looking to the overall impact of the Preamble that is is fundamental in terms of providing enduring democratic values to the people of independent India, and at the same time Preamble is a beacon light of the democratic life of our nation.

At the end, this can be safely said that whatever the constitutional value of Preamble is, it is there in our Preamble too; but more noteworthy is the fact our activist apex judiciary more dynamically interpreted our Preamble in such a way from case to case that it (Preamble) today is not only the essential part of the 'basic structure' of our Constitution but it continues to be an illuminating source of guidance to our present age and will continue to be so for the generations to come.

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